

TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE EVOLUTIONARY DEVELOPMENT OF TECHNOLOGY SCIENCE ON THE PRINCIPLE OF CONTINUITY AND CONTINUITY

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Annotation: this article provides feedback on technologies of evolutionary development based on the principle of continuity and continuity in the process of technological education.

Keywords: education, continuing education, continuity, Technology, Program, workshop, methodological support, e-textbook.

Introduction.

It is known that in 2017-2021, the state program on the implementation of the strategy of action on the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the "Year of support of active entrepreneurship, innovative ideas and technologies" established the development and adoption of a new draft of the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on education". Since the early years of independence, special attention has been paid to the radical reform of the educational system, and great works have been carried out on the development of modern knowledge and Professions at the level of World templates, growing up as physically and spiritually mature people, raising their abilities and talents, intellectual potential, raising feelings of loyalty and dedication to the motherland in the However, today, the rapidly changing times, the sharp competition in the world market and the growing demand for highly qualified personnel make it necessary to reform this industry as well. Even in our country, which has entered the next stage of development, in the past two years, important measures are being implemented aimed at radical reform of the educational system in accordance with the content of the updates carried out in all areas of our society.

On the basis of feedback from the general public and parents, 11 years of compulsory school education has been reintroduced in our country, depending on the need for personnel, the system of secondary special, vocational education is also being reformed with address and purpose. Admission quotas to higher education institutions were increased, the system of nostrification of diplomas of prestigious higher education institutions abroad was simplified, correspondence education was established in a number of areas with high demand, the system of state test tests was improved. At the same time, the system of education after higher education is also improved based on international templates, creating a wide range of conditions for the comprehensive support of scientists, their scientific and innovative activities.

In accordance with the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 6, 2020 "on additional measures to further improve the educational system", the inspection and related ministries of education are assigned tasks for ensuring the continuity of educational programs and subjects of preschool, general secondary, professional, Higher Education. It provides for the continuity of pre-school, general secondary, professional and higher education science programs and the introduction of new curricula and plans to the

educational process. Today, a corresponding roadmap has been developed to ensure the implementation of these tasks.

The lack of continuity of science programs in the continuing education system has a negative impact on the quality and effectiveness of Education. In particular, there are problems such as the repetition of inter-educational topics, the allocation of an excessive number of hours to certain topics, the content of science is based almost on theoretical data, and international studies are not integrated. In the analysis of the content of the stages of education, the repetition of 10-15 percent of topics was seen in the analysis, while continuity in 50-60 percent of topics was not provided. We are faced with such urgent tasks as normative documents of the continuing education system, analysis of the continuity of educational programs, work to prevent their recurrence between the stages in each subject, and coordination of the content of textbooks on the basis of science programs, the continuity of which is provided.

Discussion.

Teaching students to enrich their spiritual world, to realize its integrity, repeatability and harmony in the perception of being, to cultivate their thinking by expressing their life's imagination in their practical activities, to develop creativity, to create innovative ideas and to introduce them into everyday life is carried out through the block-module of Applied Sciences. In the direction of modern technology in existing higher educational institutions, the fact that the quality of training of teacher educators and staff does not correspond to the requirements of today assumes a radical revision of the teaching of technology and updating it in accordance with the requirements of the Times. At the same time, there are still problems in teaching technology, that is, when conducting practical training, which have not found a solution since many years.

The educational discipline of technology envisaged the development of technical creativity, ability, thinking in students, the further strengthening of professional orientation by teaching methods of technology-based processing of natural, metal and non-metallic materials in the course of the lesson, the formation of skills and abilities to apply in life the acquired knowledge, skills and qualifications in the field of By teaching the subject of study, special attention is paid to the development of students' ability to technical creativity, creative skills. Creation of a system for teaching technology at all stages of education for the development of technology science, development of scientific methodological support of Technology Science, strengthening the material and technical support of technology science, providing modern technologies and technologies, forming an innovative infrastructure through the introduction of digital technologies and modern methods into the process of technology education, interaction with general secondary education, it will be necessary to develop an assessment system based on the content, specifics of the science, qualification requirements and competencies that will be taught within the framework of Science and serve as a base stage for training professions and specialists selected as promising for the economy of our country, strengthening the material and technical base of Technology Science is necessary. To do this, the establishment of new types of modern educational production workshops (laboratories) taking into account international experiences and adaptation of pre-built educational production workshops to the model of a modern workshop (laboratory), modern furniture, equipment, equipment and devices, educational-methodological materials, computer,

interactive whiteboard, tablet and multimedia techniques, equipping with the internet, video surveillance systems, updating them on time, for practical training in workshops (laboratories), it is necessary to establish the provision of the necessary raw materials at the expense of the state budget, non-budgetary funds of sponsor organizations and educational institution.

Creating a system for posting information about educational and methodological complexes (textbook, exercise book, methodological manual for a teacher, multimedia application of textbooks) using a QR code for downloading and copying e-books on technology on mobile equipment, organizing distance education programs based on modern information and communication technologies, allowing you to track and master theoretical and practical activities online, it is also possible to use the platforms (Edu Market interactive-virtual education program) that impose them on electronic information keepers, the use of “cloud technologies” in educational processes, the placement of educational and methodological complexes developed in the field of technology on the Electronic Library system that allows remote use, the expansion of opportunities for their use, the gradual increase of electronic resources in, in order to download them to mobile devices, it would be advisable to create a system for posting information about electronic resources using a QR code.

In conclusion, if the above requirements are fully implemented, then competencies have been formed in which students can apply the knowledge, skills and qualifications gained on operations performed during the technological process in independent practical activities, enter into social relations on the basis of professional selection, national and universal values, become necessary in the labor market, technological literacy, critical, creative and systematic thinking,, they are formed as a person who is able to show his intellectual abilities and is spiritually harmonious.

The science of technology is the driving force for the integration of Education, Science and production, the backbone of the economy of Uzbekistan. Globalization in the field of economics, social cultural changes, improving quality indicators in personnel training, increasing the status and prestige of the science of technology, the formation of an atmosphere of creativity among students, the identification of talented students and youth, the formation of a system for organizing the selection of intellectually mature students and youth on a Republican scale.

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